

Empirical Insights into Enhanced PCM Cold Storage: Experimental Results from the ECHO Project for Sustainable Cooling

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The building sector, accounting for 26% of global GHG emissions and 30% of energy use, requires innovative solutions to reduce its carbon footprint. Latent Thermal Energy Storage (LTES) systems with phase change materials (PCMs) show promise in enhancing energy efficiency. This study, part of the HORIZON-EU ECHO project (project number 101096368), explores PCM selection for cold storage in residential air conditioning.

A 60-liter steel prototype filled with a water-ethylene glycol mixture, in which encapsulated PCMs are immersed, was developed and insulated under the ECHO project. Three PCM formulations were tested: pure water, a sodium carbonate-water solution ($\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and a further formulation of the $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution with steel shavings to improve thermal conductivity. Each formulation underwent three-hour charge-discharge cycles at residential cooling temperatures.

Results indicate significant gains in heat absorption, release, and stability, confirming the effectiveness of optimized PCM formulations for sustainable residential cooling solutions.

Keywords: PCM, LTES, Sustainable Cooling, HVAC&R systems, Thermal Conductivity Enhancement.

INTRODUCTION

Effectively addressing climate change necessitates focused actions in high-emission sectors, with the building sector accounting for 26% of global GHG emissions and 30% of energy consumption [1]. This highlights the critical need for innovative solutions to reduce buildings' carbon footprint, aligned with the EU's climate targets such as Fit-for-55 and REPowerEU [2,3]. Thermal Energy Storage (TES), particularly Latent Thermal Energy Storage (LTES) using Phase Change Materials (PCMs), offers promising potential due to its high energy density and ability to mitigate energy supply-demand mismatches [4]. Despite benefits like compactness and operational flexibility, LTES faces challenges related to installation costs and limited large-scale deployment, especially in cooling applications [5]. Cooling Thermal Energy Storage (CTES) systems—both passive and active—are gaining research interest, particularly for sub-zero applications, yet remain underdeveloped due to technical and economic constraints. Numerous studies have explored strategies to enhance PCM thermal conductivity, including encapsulation and

use of additives, showing improved performance over conventional systems. However, experimental validation is still insufficient, especially for system-level evaluations and economic analyses [6,7]. In this context, the HORIZON-EU Project ECHO (Efficient Compact Modular Thermal Energy Storage System, Project No. 101096368) aims to develop a modular, sustainable, and digitally controlled TES system combining PCMs and thermochemical materials for versatile applications in heating, cooling, and domestic hot water [8]. As part of this study, a 60-liter steel prototype filled with a water-ethylene glycol mixture was tested to assess the effectiveness of three different PCM formulations—pure water, the eutectic $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution, and a steel-shavings-enhanced formulation—under residential cooling conditions using repeated charge-discharge cycles. Results were compared in terms of heat absorption, release, and thermal stability to assess if advantages are obtained through the use of the standard and enhanced eutectics compared to water. Doing so the effectiveness of optimized PCM formulations for sustainable cold storage in buildings can be demonstrated.

GEOMETRY

Fig 1. Prototype geometry

The tested prototype was designed with a cylindrical geometry optimized for PCM performance evaluation. It consists of five vertically arranged HDPE internal tubes (Tube ice© from PCM products), each filled with the selected PCM, enclosed within an external steel cylinder containing a 70/30 weight ratio mixture of water and ethylene glycol (Figure 1), working as heat transfer fluid and moved by an electric pump. The total accumulator volume spans 900 mm in height, comprising approximately 59 liters in the outer cylinder and 6.4 liters within the internal tubes. High-

efficiency thermal insulation, utilizing a PU-PCM composite developed by the Istanbul Technical University and manufactured by Ideakim©, envelops the structure to ensure minimal thermal losses during the charge-discharge cycles.

METHODOLOGY

For each PCM, the test was carried out in both charging and discharging modes of the thermal storage unit, following inlet temperature conditions for the heat transfer fluid compatible with the largest air-conditioning system foreseen by the ECHO project, into which the final storage unit will eventually be integrated. The operating conditions are summarized in Table 1. For each PCM, three discharging tests and three charging tests were performed to ensure repeatability and consistency of the results.

Table 1. Test conditions

Parameter	Charging	Discharging
Inlet Temperature [°C]	-10	15
Pump Velocity [rpm]	3500	3500
Test Duration [h]	3	3

RESULTS

Compared to the baseline case using bidistilled water as the PCM within the cold storage unit, a

tangible improvement in storage capacity within the test duration was achieved through the use of the eutectic $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution. Furthermore, the addition of steel shavings to the eutectic formulation proved effective in addressing one of the primary limitations of PCMs—low thermal conductivity—by enhancing the responsiveness of the system and increasing the heat exchange rate during the charging and discharging phases.

CONCLUSIONS

The experimental results confirm that optimized PCM formulations, particularly the $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ eutectic and its steel-shaving-enhanced variant, significantly improve cold storage performance over pure water. These enhancements led to greater heat storage capacity, improved thermal stability, and faster heat exchange. The findings support the integration of advanced PCMs in modular LTES systems for efficient and sustainable residential cooling, in line with the objectives of the HORIZON-EU ECHO project.

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